

Luis Gracia Gaspar (Universidad de Alcalá)

Pilar Gómez Bedate, Ángel Crespo y el olvidado exilio español en Puerto Rico: ¿Mayagüez, páramo cultural?

Resumen

La historiografía sobre el exilio español en Puerto Rico parece haberse centrado en el espacio de Río Piedras, residencia de Juan Ramón Jiménez, Pedro Salinas o María Zambrano; sin embargo, la esfera de Mayagüez albergó una estimable vida intelectual relacionada con expatriados republicanos. Los escritores y filólogos Pilar Gómez Bedate y Ángel Crespo iluminaron el valor de ese espacio, como se estudia a partir del relato ‘Una nueva vida’ (2018) de Gómez Bedate. Ambos se habían trasterrado a Mayagüez en 1967 gracias a Dámaso Alonso, próximo a los dos y pieza clave en su salida y relación. No obstante, ese entorno se les antojó un yermo cultural que determinó su actividad, opacada por su exilio tardío de España. Explorar su significativo sentir elucidada la desatención hacia Mayagüez, donde resulta crucial la trayectoria del recinto universitario.

Abstract

The historiography on the Spanish exile in Puerto Rico seems to have focused on the space of Río Piedras, place of residence of Juan Ramón Jiménez, Pedro Salinas or María Zambrano. However, the Mayagüez sphere involved remarkable intellectual life linked to republican expatriates. The writers and philologists Pilar Gómez Bedate and Ángel Crespo clarified the value of that space, as is studied from Gómez Bedate’s story ‘Una nueva vida’ (2018). Both went into exile in Mayagüez in 1967 due to Dámaso Alonso, close to the two and key to their departure and relationship. However, that space turned out for them as a cultural wasteland which determined their activity, overshadowed by their late exile from Spain. Explore its significant judgement elucidates the lack of academic attention towards Mayagüez, where the history of the university campus is crucial.

**The Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM) version is the last author version of an article which was submitted to the journal editor for publication, likely a Word document or equivalent. This is the version which may be deposited under the conditions above, not the final publisher version which is a PDF with copyediting and typesetting performed on the work.*